

A comprehensive item bank of internal validity issues of relevance to in vitro toxicology studies

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43 Disclaimers

44 The author Ingrid L. Druwe is employed at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. The
45 views expressed in this manuscript are those of the authors and do not necessarily
46 represent the views or policies of the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.

47 The author Andrew A. Rooney is employed at the U.S. National Institute of Environmental
48 Health Sciences. The views expressed in this manuscript are those of the authors and do
49 not necessarily represent the views or policies of the U.S. National Institute of Environmental
50 Health Sciences.

51 Abstract

52 **Context:** *In vitro* toxicology studies are increasingly being included as evidence in
53 systematic reviews and chemical risk assessments. INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the
54 internal validity of *in vitro* studies, is currently under development. The first step in
55 developing INVITES-IN involves the creation of an “item bank”, an overview of study
56 assessment concepts that may be relevant to evaluating the internal validity of *in vitro*
57 toxicology studies. The item bank and methodology for its creation presented in this
58 manuscript are intended to be a general resource for supporting the development of
59 appraisal tools for *in vitro* toxicology studies and potentially other study designs.

60 **Methods:** We derived the item bank from seven literature sources (one existing item bank
61 created from a systematic review of assessment criteria for *in vitro* studies, and six
62 purposively sampled study appraisal tools) and the transcripts of three focus groups.
63 Assessment criteria plausibly relating to internal validity were abstracted from the literature
64 sources and focus group transcripts, disaggregated into individual criteria, then normalised to
65 express in the simplest achievable language the core issue in each criterion – an “item bank”
66 of assessment concepts. The items were then mapped onto a set of bias domains. We
67 conducted simple descriptive statistical analyses and visualisations to describe patterns in
68 the dataset and developed recommendations for the use and development of the item bank.

69 **Results:** The item bank contains 405 items of potential relevance to evaluating the internal
70 validity of *in vitro* toxicology studies.

71 **Discussion:** To our knowledge, this is the second item bank of any kind to have been
72 created for toxicology studies, and the first to use focus groups as a data source alongside
73 literature analysis. The large number of items contributed by focus group discussions
74 suggests this is an efficient method for capturing internal validity issues that are not easily
75 identifiable in the literature. We believe our item bank and methodology for its creation will be
76 a useful resource for supporting the development of appraisal tools. Due to the broad
77 applicability of many items in the item bank, it may be informative for study designs beyond
78 the *in vitro* domain.

79 1. Introduction

80 Systematic reviews are increasingly being conducted in toxicology, environmental
81 health, and chemical risk assessment (Menon et al., 2022). An important part of the

82 review methodology is the evaluation of internal validity, i.e. the extent to which the
83 design, conduct, and reporting of a study are likely to have prevented bias. While many tools
84 have been created for assessing validity of *in vitro* studies, to date there is no consensus as
85 to which, if any, of these tools ought to be used for the assessment of internal validity of *in*
86 *vitro* studies (Tran et al., 2021). To address this issue, we are conducting the INVITES-IN
87 (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity) project. The objective of INVITES-IN is to
88 select, modify, or develop an appraisal tool for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro*
89 studies, with an initial focus on eukaryotic cell culture studies.

90 The creation of INVITES-IN consists of four methodological stages, that we refer to as
91 “studies”:

- 92 • Study 1. Creating a comprehensive database of issues that may affect the internal
93 validity of *in vitro* studies of any design.
- 94 • Study 2. Prioritising issues from the database according to their relevance to the
95 assessment of internal validity of eukaryotic cell culture systems.
- 96 • Study 3. Creating a beta version of an appraisal tool based on analysis of the prioritised
97 issues identified in stage 2.
- 98 • Study 4. Creating a final release version of the tool, based on user-testing of the beta
99 version.

100 Due to the complexity of the INVITES-IN project, we are publishing our methods and results
101 in three manuscripts. The present manuscript describes the methods and results for Study 1.
102 A second manuscript will describe Study 2. The third manuscript will describe Studies 3 and
103 4. The planned methods for all four INVITES-IN studies, the creation and user testing of
104 INVITES-IN are described in two protocols (Mathisen et al., 2023; Svendsen et al., 2023).

105 1.1 Objectives

106 The objective of this study is to create a comprehensive database of issues relating to the
107 design, conduct, or reporting of *in vitro* studies that may introduce bias into their results or
108 findings. Following Page et al. (2020) and Whiting et al. (2017), we call such a database an
109 “item bank”.

110 It should be noted that while INVITES-IN is ultimately aimed at creating a tool for assessing
111 risk of bias in studies of eukaryotic cell culture systems, the item bank includes issues for *in*
112 *vitro* studies of any design.

113 2. Methods

114 In their proposed framework for developing quality assessment tools, Whiting and
115 colleagues recommend an “item generation” step be part of tool development methodology
116 (Whiting et al., 2017). However, what constitutes best practice in item generation is not, as
117 far as we are aware, a settled matter. Our item bank development methodology follows
118 Whaley et al. (2024) and consists of two main stages, summarised below then described
119 more fully in the subsequent sections of this manuscript. The full details of the methodology
120 are in our preregistered study protocol (Svendson et al., 2023).

121 **Stage 1. Issue discovery**

122 The objective of this stage is to identify a comprehensive set of issues relating to the design,
123 conduct, or reporting of *in vitro* studies that may introduce bias into their results or findings.

124 Our method for this stage is to abstract from (a) a purposive sample of tools designed for
125 assessing the internal validity of scientific studies and (b) focus group transcripts a
126 comprehensive list of issues that researchers believe impact the internal validity of *in vitro*
127 studies.

128 We chose this approach because three separate reviews have indicated that none of the
129 existing quality assessment tools for *in vitro* studies individually cover all critical aspects for
130 assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies (Paiva Barbosa et al., 2023; Tran et al.,
131 2021; Whaley et al., 2024), and we believed that focus groups with *in vitro* experts would
132 capture important bias issues that have not yet been incorporated into validity assessment
133 tools.

134 **Stage 2. Issue analysis**

135 The objective of this stage is to derive linguistically minimalist expressions of the study
136 assessment concepts identified in the stage 1 (i.e. create the database of “items”) and
137 organising these according to bias themes.

138 We chose this approach because the way that bias issues are presented in appraisal tools
139 and focus group discussions is heterogeneous and complex. This can make it challenging to
140 discern precisely what issue is being addressed by a criterion in a tool or a point of expert
141 discussion, and to compare tool criteria or discussion points to determine if they are in fact
142 about the same issue. We therefore disaggregated complex appraisal criteria into their
143 component issues and sought to eliminate irrelevant linguistic differences in how appraisal
144 criteria are expressed in different tools and contexts (a process we refer to as
145 “normalisation”). We also organised items into bias domains to help structure the database
146 and make it easier to use in later stages of the INVITES-IN project.

147 The process for issue analysis is illustrated in Figure 1.

148 2.1 Issues discovery

149 We used two sources for creation of the item bank: first, literature (six appraisal tools and
150 one systematic review, see section 2.1.1 for more details); and second, experts with
151 extensive experience with *in vitro* studies (called “domain experts”) participating in focus
152 group discussions (see section 2.1.2). We conducted the literature analysis first, then
153 supplemented the literature with the additional items discovered through the focus group
154 discussions.

155 2.1.1 Literature sources

156 Items were abstracted from the literature sources as listed in the protocol (Svendsen et al.,
157 2023) with one additional tool (ROBINS-E). The literature sources included a selection of
158 published and widely used validity assessment tools, and an existing item bank covering
159 study appraisal concepts included in 67 *in vitro* appraisal tools (Whaley et al., 2023).

160 The literature sources included tools for assessment of *in vitro* studies, human studies, and
161 animal experimental studies. We included assessment tools for non *in vitro* studies based on
162 our experience that assessment concepts are quite generalizable for different types of study,
163 and therefore that newer risk of bias tools even for epidemiological research may include
164 concepts that could be applicable to *in vitro* studies. This way we aimed to capture emerging
165 developments in risk of bias assessment methods and criteria that may not yet have been
166 incorporated into tools within the *in vitro* toxicology literature. The literature sources are listed
167 in Table 1.

168 **Table 1. Literature sources for item bank.**

Source ID	Source Name or Title	Source Type	Source Citation
IRIS	IRIS: ORD Staff Handbook for Developing IRIS Assessments	Guidance on study appraisal for IRIS assessments	EPA (2022)
OHAT	OHAT: Protocol to evaluate the evidence for an association between perfluorooctanic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) exposure and immunotoxicity	Bias assessment tool	NTP OHAT (2015)
ROB2	ROB 2: A revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials	Bias assessment tool	Sterne et al. (2019)
ROBINS-E	ROBINS-E: Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Exposure	Bias assessment tool	Higgins et al. (2024)
SciRAP	SciRAP: Development of the SciRAP Approach for Evaluating the Reliability and Relevance of <i>in vitro</i> Toxicity Data	Study appraisal tool for supporting risk assessment	Roth et al. (2021)
Cooper	Study sensitivity: Evaluating the ability to detect effects in systematic reviews of chemical exposures	Guidance on assessing study sensitivity	Cooper et al. (2016)
Whaley	Literature-based discovery of assessment criteria for <i>in vitro</i> studies: a method and item bank	Item bank	Whaley et al. (2023)

169 2.1.2 Focus groups

170 *2.1.2.1 Recruitment of focus group participants*

171 Eligible focus group discussion participants were scientists with or without systematic review
172 experience that are active in the field of *in vitro* studies in academia, governmental
173 institutions (including risk assessment institutions and research institutes) or private research

174 institutes, at postdoctoral level or higher, and level B1 English speakers. By “active in the
175 field of *in vitro* studies” we mean having practical experience in conducting *in vitro* studies,
176 and/or experience in analysing or evaluating data from such studies.

177 The focus group discussion participants were nominated by members in the project group
178 and the scientific advisory group (see “project governance”).

179 Potential participants were invited to participate with the aim of achieving (1) an equal
180 gender distribution, (2) a reasonable demographic and regional distribution, and (3) enough
181 participants to have three groups of six to eight people. Potential participants were contacted
182 via email and sent information about the project, the purpose of the focus group discussions
183 and the method, that the results would be anonymised, the withdrawal procedure, the
184 financial source, and the approximate time for the focus group discussions (Supplemental
185 Material 1). Thirty potentially eligible participants were invited in the period of 16 May to 12
186 June 2023. All participants who accepted the invitation actively confirmed their consent to
187 participate in the research.

188 Twenty participants were recruited and participated in the focus group discussions: six in
189 group 1, eight in group 2, and six in group 3. An overview of the characteristics of the
190 participants is given in Supplemental Material 2. The participants were mostly from Europe
191 and North America, and worked in various sectors (e.g. government agencies, academia).
192 Most had extensive expertise with *in vitro* studies and chemical risk assessment. While we
193 sought to have an equal distribution of gender, the individuals who had the expertise along
194 with availability to participate were overwhelmingly female (15 female to 5 males).

195 *2.1.2.2 Focus group discussion sessions*

196 Focus group participants were engaged in open-ended conversation about how, in their
197 opinion, bias can be introduced into *in vitro* studies. Each focus group met twice virtually, for
198 90 minutes in each meeting, using Microsoft Teams. The focus group discussions were
199 audio-recorded and machine-transcribed using the transcribe function in Microsoft Teams
200 classic (June 2023), with transcription errors corrected only when it was judged to have
201 changed the meaning of the concepts of interest to the item identification process.

202 Transcripts were anonymized and original recordings were deleted after 30 days. The focus
203 group discussions were moderated by one investigator (PW) and assisted by another
204 investigator (GEV). The discussion was structured according to the bias domains used to
205 organise the items extracted from the literature. For each domain, the moderator presented

206 the name of the bias domain, the number of items that had been associated with the bias
207 from the literature-based component of the item bank, and the definition of the bias.
208 Discussion was paced by the moderator to attempt to work through all domains across the
209 two sessions. The order in which domains were presented was different for each group, with
210 priority given to domains that had overall received less discussion in previous focus groups
211 (with the exception that when starting a discussion with a new group, a more intuitive domain
212 would be chosen to get conversation going). Participants were led in discussion of how the
213 domain might be relevant to the *in vitro* research context, and asked for examples from their
214 practical research experience of how systematic error can be introduced into an *in vitro*
215 study. A third investigator (HMA) participated in all sessions, taking back-up notes in case of
216 technical failure and to support any necessary correction of the machine-generated
217 transcripts. The information shown to the participants of each focus group is in Supplemental
218 Material 3.

219 Participants were given the option to send by email their thoughts and considerations on the
220 relevance of the discussed bias domains and items for *in vitro* studies to the project group
221 within a week after each discussion. One comment was received and added to the analysis.

222 2.2 Issue analysis

223 The analytical process by which the bias issues abstracted from the literature sources and
224 focus groups are interpreted into items is shown in Figure 1. In the first stage of issue
225 analysis, bias-related issues were abstracted from the included literature sources and the
226 focus group transcripts. For the literature sources, two investigators (PW and GEV)
227 independently abstracted bias-related criteria from each source, focusing on any section of a
228 source that seemed to be presenting a list or table of study quality criteria. They discussed
229 and reconciled inconsistencies in the results of their abstraction process.

230 The transcripts were independently annotated in Microsoft Word by two investigators (HMA
231 and GEV) for instances of participants indicating specific ways in which bias can be
232 introduced into an *in vitro* study (see Supplemental Material 4). After each transcript was
233 independently annotated, the two copies were combined into a single document. Two
234 investigators (HMA and GEV) went through the combined document to reach a consensus
235 on annotation. After consensus was reached, one investigator (HMA) transferred the data
236 (time stamp, data extract, annotated text) to an Excel file.

238 **Figure 1. Flow chart of the process of analysing bias issues discovered in appraisal tools and focus group discussion.** The flow chart
239 shows how issues and appraisal tool criteria are normalised to create item bank items, with illustrative examples from three criteria sources
240 (two tools and the focus group discussions). The flow chart shows progression from raw criterion, through interpretation into core concepts,
241 normalisation for linguistic consistency, and the classification of each item under the most relevant bias domain.

242 The nine hours of focus group discussions yielded a large number of potential issues for
243 normalisation (n=911). To reduce the size of the task, two investigators (PW and GEV) pre-
244 analysed the transcript annotations, independently answering for each annotated issue “Are
245 you sure this is about bias?” and “Are you sure this is a new item?”. Issues for which both
246 investigators answered yes to both questions were advanced directly to issue analysis.
247 When investigators disagreed on either question, they discussed their responses to come to
248 consensus on whether an item ought to be excluded from or advanced to issue analysis.

249 The next stage of issue analysis was conducted as an iterative process whereby two
250 investigators (GEV and PW) independently proposed their interpretation of the core bias
251 issues represented by an abstracted criterion or discussion point. Sometimes this involved
252 splitting complex criteria or discussion points into multiple individual concepts. The
253 investigators then compared their interpretations and reconciled differences through
254 discussion. This process resulted in a list of draft items for the item bank.

255 The draft items often had redundant wording or otherwise lacked linguistic precision. These
256 items were therefore reformulated a final time to remove unnecessary phrasing and
257 eliminate as many trivial linguistic differences as was possible. The reformulations were
258 proposed by PW and commented on by GEV, with disagreements about appropriate
259 formulation discussed by the two investigators until consensus was reached. This process
260 resulted in the final "normalised" set of items that constitute the item bank.

261 2.2.1 Domain mapping

262 Each item was categorised according to the single best-fitting bias domains relating to the
263 item. Categorisation decisions were made by one investigator (PW), with another (GEV)
264 checking for agreement. Disagreements were resolved by discussion. The bias domains and
265 definitions were taken from the Scientific Evidence Code System (SEVCO) research
266 methods ontology (Alper et al., 2021b; FEvIR Platform Version 0.80.0, 06.12.2022).

267 The list of domains and their definitions and identifiers are shown in Table 2.

268 We chose the SEVCO domains because the grounding and consensus process used for
269 developing their definitions (Alper et al., 2021a) makes them, in our opinion, the most
270 comprehensive and robust available to us at the time of the conduct of our work. We
271 modified one domain (“Timing of Study Termination Bias” SEVCO:00370, originally “Early
272 study termination bias”) to reflect potential for bias from allowing an *in vitro* study to run on

273 longer than originally planned, as well as from being stopped earlier than planned. We
 274 added two domains to support classification and analysis (“Metabias” and “Other”) to capture
 275 items that did not fit under the other bias domains (“metabias” was used for items that
 276 appear to affect multiple bias domains; “other” was for items that did not appear to relate to
 277 any bias domain). These domains are not intended to represent “true” biases. Four SEVCO
 278 domains (Mixed Methods Research Bias; Predictive Model Research Bias; Qualitative
 279 Research Bias; Synthesis Bias) ended up with no items and were therefore unused in the
 280 item bank.

281 **Table 2. Bias domains used for classifying item bank items.**

Bias Domain	Definition	Source	Identifier
Analysis Bias	A bias related to the analytic process applied to the data.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00021
Attrition Bias	A bias due to absence of expected participation or data collection after selection for study inclusion.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00019
Choice-of-Question Bias	A bias in research design in which the research question (that the study is designed to answer) is inappropriate for the context.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00018
Conflicted Interests Bias	A bias in which decision makers influencing research design, conduct, analysis or reporting have goals or motivations that conflict with scientific research objectives.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00027
Confounding Covariate Bias	A situation in which the effect or association between an exposure or outcome is distorted by another variable. For confounding covariate bias to occur the distorting variable must be (1) associated with the exposure and the outcome, (2) not in the causal pathway between exposure	SEVCO	SEVCO:00016

Bias Domain	Definition	Source	Identifier
	and outcome, and (3) unequally distributed between the groups being compared.		
Detection Bias	A bias due to distortions in any process involved in the determination of the recorded values for a variable.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00020
Timing of Study Termination Bias*	A bias due to the decision to end the study earlier or later than planned. <i>*Modified from the original SEVCO term, "early study termination bias", defined as "a bias due to the decision to end the study earlier than planned"</i>	SEVCO	SEVCO:00370*
Performance Bias	A bias resulting from differences between the received exposure and the intended exposure.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00017
Reporting Bias	A bias due to distortions in the selection of or representation of information in study results or research findings.	SEVCO	SEVCO:00023
Selection Bias	A bias resulting from methods used to select subjects or data, factors that influence initial study participation, or differences between the study sample and the population of interest	SEVCO	SEVCO:00002
Metabias	A general distorting influence on investigator decision-making that may bias the results or findings of a study	Added by project team	INVITE:00003
Other	A distortion in results due to factors other than those described in the SEVCO terms	Added by	INVITE:00001

Bias Domain	Definition	Source	Identifier
		project team	

282

283 2.3 Deviations from protocol

284 We made the following changes to the methods described in the original protocol (Svendsen
285 et al., 2023):

- 286 • We added the Risk Of Bias In Non-randomized Studies - of Exposure (ROBINS-E) tool
287 (Higgins et al., 2024) to the set of literature sources, as we judged it could be important
288 in broadening the scope of the issues covered by the item bank.
- 289 • We excluded the systematic review conducted by Tran et al. (2021) because it did not
290 present in its results or supplemental materials a list of issues or criteria applied by the
291 appraisal tools.
- 292 • The modification of “Early termination bias” and adding of two additional domains were
293 not planned.
- 294 • We added the first-pass step to analysis of issues from the focus group discussions, to
295 make it feasible to analyse an unexpectedly large number of potential items.

296 3. Results

297 405 unique bias items were included in the item bank. We abstracted from our included
298 literature sources and focus group discussions 414 appraisal criteria and discussion points
299 of plausible relevance to the internal validity of *in vitro* studies. After normalisation, this
300 yielded 405 unique items in our item bank. Because some items occur in more than one
301 source, our eight sources contributed 497 items in total.

302 The item bank is available in .xlsx format (Microsoft Excel) in Supplemental Materials 5. This
303 file consists of seven sheets, as follows:

- 304 • **Sheet 0 "Information"**. The information sheet that provides guidance on the
305 contents of the item bank file.
- 306 • **Sheet 1 "Item Bank"**. The item bank, consisting of the reference numbers, unique
307 items (n=405), and the bias domains under which each item has been categorised.

- 308 Each item has a unique reference number to facilitate identification and tracking
309 through the analysis process.
- 310 • **Sheet 2 "Items by Source"**. The item bank, including the source and original
311 criterion or discussion point from which each item was derived. Because some items
312 appear in multiple sources, the total number of records in this sheet (n=497) is higher
313 than the total number of items (n=405).
 - 314 • **Sheet 3 "Abstracted Criteria"**. The full list of criteria and discussion points
315 abstracted from the literature sources and focus group discussions, that were
316 interpreted into the items.
 - 317 • **Sheet 4 "Included Criteria"**. The criteria and discussion points containing concepts
318 that ended up being interpreted into items and included in the item bank. This sheet
319 shows how the criteria and discussion points were interpreted into items by the
320 investigators.
 - 321 • **Sheet 5 "Excluded Criteria"**. The criteria and discussion points that were not
322 interpreted into items in the item bank.
 - 323 • **Sheet 6 "Lookups"**. The source for the drop-down lists of bias items, designed to
324 reduce data input errors when creating the item bank.

325 Sheets 1 and 2 have been set up with filters to assist with exploring the item bank, allowing
326 e.g. only items associated with analysis bias to be displayed (sheet 1), or only items
327 associated with a specific source (sheet 2). The sheets are locked but not password
328 protected to prevent accidental editing. To filter the data in the sheets, the user should right-
329 click the tab for the sheet they are interested in filtering and select "Pause Protection".

330 The relative contribution of items from different sources separated by bias domains is shown
331 in Figure 2.

332 Detection bias (n=104), performance bias (n=77), and selection bias (n=70) are the domains
333 with the most items. Two domains (choice-of-question bias and timing of study termination
334 bias) did not have any related items in the literature sources, with items coming exclusively
335 from focus group discussions (n=5 and n=3 respectively).

336 Items relating to confounding covariate bias (n=7) were contributed by tools designed for
337 assessing the internal validity of epidemiological studies. These were considered by the
338 focus groups as potentially important for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies that
339 use primary biological samples; however, as this type of study is outside the scope of

340 INVITES-IN at this time, this issue was not discussed in detail and the focus groups added
341 no further items for this domain.

342 Only three items relating to conflicted interest bias were derived from the literature sources.
343 The focus group discussions contributed six items, to give eight items in total under this
344 domain after removal of duplicates. Conflicted interest bias was considered important by the
345 focus groups, with several examples presented of where participants were concerned that
346 this had impacted studies; however, the groups found it challenging to identify specific
347 criteria for how conflict of interest could be assessed independently of the impact it has on
348 decisions about how to design, conduct, or report a study.

349 Metabias is a very heterogeneous domain. It includes issues such as “blinding of operator”
350 (item 299) that are both highly specific study design issues yet impact multiple bias domains.
351 Importantly, the metabias domain includes “inappropriate deviation from protocol” (item
352 4048). We believe is the only reference in the whole item bank to the potentially important
353 issue of inappropriate exploitation of researcher degrees of freedom (Wicherts et al., 2016)
354 when conducting and reporting research.

355 The two literature sources we included that were not originally designed for *in vitro* studies
356 (ROB2 for human randomised controlled trials and ROBINS-E for human observational
357 studies of environmental exposures) contributed 24% of the items in the item bank (118 of
358 497 items before deduplication). The focus group discussions contributed 28% of the items
359 in the item bank (139 of 497 items before deduplication).

360

361

362 **Figure 2. Unique bias items, disaggregated by source and in total from all sources.**

363 Note that the total count of items from all sources (column: ALL SOURCES) is lower than the
 364 sum of items from individual sources (columns: Cooper, IRIS, etc.) because some items
 365 appear in more than one source and are deduplicated in the final count. We used the
 366 Obscure Reference Generator (Version 2.1; Esolang, 2014), to generate Figure 2, the code
 367 for generating the figure is available in Supplemental Material 6.

368 **4. Discussion**

369 We have created a comprehensive bank of 405 items of potential relevance for the
 370 assessment of the internal validity of *in vitro* toxicology studies. We hope this provides a
 371 valuable dataset for informing the development of tools that include assessment of the

372 internal validity of *in vitro* studies, and a methodology that is useful for appraisal tool
373 development in general. Through our normalisation process we believe we advance on the
374 methods recommended by Whiting et al. (2017) and used by Page et al. (2020), while by
375 conducting focus group discussions we identified significantly more issues than we would
376 have done through following an exclusively literature-based approach such as that of
377 Whaley et al. (2024).

378 To support the interpretation and use of our item bank in tool development, and the reuse of
379 our method, we discuss the following below:

- 380 • Our normalisation and exclusion decisions
- 381 • The importance of focus group discussions
- 382 • Some observations about the tools we included as literature sources
- 383 • Guidance on how to use the item bank

384 4.1 Normalisation and exclusion decisions

385 Our process for analysing criteria from literature sources and discussion points from the
386 focus group discussions into normalised items was naturally subjective and completed in
387 finite time. We expect that additional rounds of analysis would have eliminated further trivial
388 differences between items and reduced the number of items overall (items 202 “exposure
389 misclassification” and 208 “misclassification of exposure” are a particularly obvious example
390 of where we missed conceptual duplicates). Other researchers could reasonably argue that
391 differences between items such as 105 “storage of test compound” and 2097 “storage of test
392 materials” are functionally equivalent and that preserving the difference unhelpfully inflates
393 the number of items in the item bank.

394 Our counterargument to this point is we felt that preserving even small conceptual
395 differences might be significant to the development of an INVITES-IN appraisal tool in a way
396 we cannot anticipate during the item identification process. We felt that if we normalised
397 away subtle differences, we risked losing important nuance and context that we would not be
398 able to retrieve later. This could have a particular impact on the more detailed prompts,
399 elicitation questions, and guidance that will form part of the eventual INVITES-IN tool. We
400 therefore normalised items in such a way as to preserve detail, and it is in the post-Delphi
401 stage of INVITES-IN (when we create the beta version of our tool) that we will remove detail
402 in the items that is not helpful for our context.

403 Our exclusion decisions were similarly subjective. Other researchers may not agree with
404 them, and it is possible we excluded concepts that should have been part of our final item
405 bank. A limitation of our method is that we did not document all reasons for our exclusions
406 (see Supplemental Materials 6, sheet 5) as it was too time-intensive to give informative
407 reasons for hundreds of exclusion decisions based on sometimes lengthy discussion. In
408 general, we would note that using a larger team of researchers to make exclusion and
409 normalisation decisions, and conducting more rounds of normalisation, would lead to
410 improved results. However, with hundreds of items and each round taking many person
411 hours (we estimate two people need 20 hours of discussion for 400 items), a decision must
412 be made as to the cost-benefit trade-off of running each round of analysis.

413 To compensate for limitations and potential differences of opinion around our approach and
414 resulting items, we have included in our item bank all the uninterpreted source criteria and
415 discussion points, to give other teams all the materials they need to reinterpret our data.

416 It should also be noted that this study was a discovery exercise with the sole aim of
417 collecting items for the creation of our item bank. Any reinterpretation of original tools and
418 criteria for our specific purposes should not be interpreted as critique of those tools: it is a
419 linguistic process of simplification that removes detail and information about context, to make
420 it easier to identify and analyse as many as possible of the core internal validity concepts
421 being expressed by the tools in aggregate.

422 4.2 The importance of focus groups and including non *in vitro* tools

423 In our opinion, including expert opinion in the preparation of the item bank via focus group
424 discussions was very effective. The focus group discussions provided new insight into how
425 participants considered, contextualised, and defined the different aspects of bias,
426 significantly extending the range of issues that would have been covered had we focused
427 exclusively on the literature for our item discovery process. The focus group discussions
428 added a large number of items to analysis, detection, performance, and selection bias, with
429 the practical experience of the participants able to add many considerations to bias domains
430 of which the literature only had partial coverage.

431 It is important to note that the first focus group contributed 74 new discussion items, the
432 second 30, and the third group 28. The fact that a large proportion of new items were still
433 being discovered in the third focus group discussion suggests that there are more items yet
434 to be discovered. Therefore, coverage of all critical aspects for the assessment of internal

435 validity in *in vitro* studies, even in our item bank, remains incomplete and additional focus
436 groups would still be of high value.

437 Our assumption that tools not designed for *in vitro* studies would be useful for *in vitro*
438 contexts was also validated by our results, with ROB2 and ROBINS-E contributing many
439 items that we otherwise would have missed had we excluded them.

440 4.3 Observations about included tools

441 While interpreting assessment criteria into items, we noted three issues that may be
442 informative for the future development of appraisal tools in general.

443 4.3.1 Multiple issues covered by single criteria

444 Firstly, there is a tendency for tools to collapse multiple points of evaluation into a single
445 criterion, in a way that may be problematic. For example, the uninterpreted criterion number
446 126 (see Supplemental Materials 5, sheet 2 – reference numbers are in column B) states:
447 “Was the exposure period, timing (i.e., cell passage number, insufficient culture maturity for
448 the adequate expression of mature cell markers; insufficient treatment or measurement
449 duration for the production of protein above the level of detection), frequency, and duration
450 of exposure sensitive for the assay/model system of interest, particularly in the absence of a
451 positive control?”. This combines multiple aspects of exposure and use of positive controls,
452 into a single prompt. The uninterpreted criterion number 130, from the same tool, states:
453 “Are there concerns regarding the need for positive controls (e.g., concerns that the effects
454 of interest may be inhibited or otherwise poorly manifest in the test system, for example due
455 to differences from *in vivo* biology)? If used, was the selected positive test substance (and
456 dose) reasonable and appropriate and was the intended positive response induced?” This
457 criterion covers several additional aspects of the use of positive controls, relating to the
458 ability of a test system to manifest an outcome of interest.

459 Combining multiple issues into a single evaluation criterion may not always be problematic,
460 for example when a criterion addresses two issues in a similar enough domain that it may
461 not make sense to divide them in a particular study assessment context. However, on some
462 occasions it may be important to separate these issues, (a) if this could affect the
463 transparency or repeatability of the appraisal process, (b) it could affect reuse of data from
464 the assessment when it is ambiguous what specific issue a judgement relates to, or (c) if it

465 leads to double-counting of issues when there is overlap of common issues across two or
466 more compound criteria.

467 4.3.2 “Study sensitivity” as an assessment domain

468 Secondly, some study appraisal tools are concerned with the “sensitivity” of study methods
469 (e.g. IRIS 2022, Cooper 2016). However, when mapping items derived from sensitivity
470 concerns onto bias domains, many of these items seemed to fit under the domain of
471 detection bias (e.g. the items “Insufficient level of exposure” (ref 53), “Insufficient duration of
472 exposure” (ref 54) “Insufficient range of doses” (ref 69), “Duration of exposure” (ref 72)).
473 Others seemed to fit under the performance bias domain (e.g. the items “Method of
474 administration of exposure” (ref 73), “Route of administration of exposure” (ref 74)) or the
475 reporting bias domain (e.g. the item “Choice of analyses reported” (ref 76)). Some sensitivity
476 criteria were excluded as relating to the precision of a study (e.g., the uninterpreted criterion
477 “Are the numbers of exposed cases adequate to detect an effect in the exposed population
478 and/or subgroups of the exposed population?” (ref 50)) or the external validity of a study
479 (e.g. the criterion “Are the outcome ascertainment methods reliable and valid; is the outcome
480 under study a sensitive indicator of the health effect of interest?” (ref 51)).

481 While it is not necessarily important how issues relating to potential systematic error are
482 divided into assessment domains, having the same concept split across two or more
483 separate domains may add unnecessary complexity to an assessment process and
484 potentially increase the risk of double-counting appraisal factors. For example, the criteria
485 “Does the exposure assessment capture the relevant window of exposure?” (ref 57) and “Is
486 the timing and duration of exposure relevant for the endpoints under study? If the sensitive
487 exposure window is unknown, is the exposure period wide enough to cover likely
488 possibilities?” (ref 71) seem closely related but are different questions in the source tool.
489 Similarly, the criteria “Variable Control: Are all introduced variables with the potential to affect
490 the results of interest controlled for and consistent across experimental groups?” (ref 85) and
491 “Are appropriate control groups for the study/assay type included? Was there a need for the
492 assay to include specific controls to reduce potential sources of underlying bias?” (ref 113)
493 appear to be covering aspects of the same issue twice in the same tool.

494 This observation should not be interpreted as a critique of the specific assessment tools, as
495 we are only making general observations across a dataset and not analysing specific tools in
496 detail. However, it may be worthwhile conducting a closer inspection and re-evaluation of the

497 principles and structure behind some study assessment processes, and its potential impact
498 on the validity of the results of the evaluation process using these tools.

499 4.3.3 Existing tools lag expert knowledge

500 Thirdly, the coverage of all critical aspects for the assessment of internal validity by existing
501 tools may not be optimal. The focus group discussions identified many new issues and were
502 the single-largest contributor of assessment items, including items to some domains that
503 were completely unmentioned in the existing tools that we sampled. *In vitro* study methods
504 are a fast-evolving field and any appraisal tool for the domain will likely need regular
505 updating to keep up with ongoing developments.

506 4.4 Guidance on how to use the item bank

507 The item bank is a database of concepts and requires further analysis when creating an
508 appraisal tool – it is like an ingredient in a recipe which cannot be consumed directly off the
509 shelf. For the beta version of INVITES-IN we are using Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data
510 Analysis Software (CAQDAS) to identify clusters of related concepts under a range of
511 possible appraisal themes that we could potentially use for structuring our appraisal tool. We
512 expect the broad themes to provide structure in the form of domains or sections of the tool;
513 for similarities between clusters of related items to be interpretable into elicitation questions;
514 and for the more granular details of the items to inform specific prompts or detailed guidance
515 on how elicitation questions in the tool should be answered.

516 In this process, we are finding it helpful to preface an item with a phrase that prompts
517 reflection on how the concept being expressed could result in issues with the internal validity
518 of a study. For example, for the item “Conditions of maintenance of cell line” we might think
519 “Problems with conditions of maintenance of cell line that introduce bias” to keep us focused
520 on interpreting the item for our task. A different team using our item bank to create a
521 reporting checklist might prefer to interpret items for their context as follows: “Problems with
522 reporting the conditions of maintenance of the cell line that compromise the reproducibility of
523 the study”. Our item bank is intended as a general resource, which means the user must
524 interpret the items for their specific context.

525 5. Conclusion

526 We have created a comprehensive item bank of 405 unique bias items that may be relevant
527 for assessing the internal validity of *in vitro* studies. The inclusion of focus group discussions

528 with *in vitro* experts was of significant value in our method, adding more than a hundred
529 additional bias items and enhancing our understanding of the challenges associated with
530 assessing *in vitro* studies. We believe that both our method used to create the
531 comprehensive item bank, and the item bank itself, will be useful for other researchers
532 creating validity assessment tools. Overall, we believe our item bank to be a valuable
533 dataset of bias concepts that can support the development of tools for the assessment of *in*
534 *vitro* studies in the field of toxicology.

535 Project governance

536 This study is part of the project “Next Generation Risk Assessment in Practice” (VKM, 2023),
537 included in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC)
538 (PARC, 2023). A project group is responsible for the creation of INVITES-IN. A scientific
539 advisory group consisting of experts in methods for tool development, systematic review
540 methods, chemical risk assessment, toxicology, and/or *in vitro* models has been established
541 to provide the project group with strategic guidance and support during the process of
542 creating INVITES-IN (VKM, 2023).

543 Abbreviations

544 FGD: focus group discussion

545 SEVCO: Scientific Evidence Code System

546 Acknowledgements

547 We thank Miles Davenport (University of New South Wales) for comments on draft versions
548 of this manuscript.

549 Definitions / Glossary

550 The definitions have been updated since publication of our study protocol (Svendsen et al.,
551 2023).

552 **Bias** is a systematic error, or deviation from the truth, in the results or findings of individual
553 studies or across studies. Systematic error may be introduced through limitations in the
554 design, conduct, or reporting of a study.

555 **Bias domains** are a conceptual framework for organising the limitations in conduct, design,
556 or reporting of a study that have affected the internal validity of a study. Bias domains in the
557 present study include but are not limited to detection, performance, and selection bias.

558 **Criteria** are the issues that have to be fulfilled for bias to be avoided. In tools for evaluation
559 of risk of bias, the users of the tool will often answer signalling questions in order to
560 determine whether the criteria have been fulfilled.

561 **Internal validity** is the extent to which the design, conduct, and reporting of a study are
562 likely to have prevented bias.

563 **Items** are linguistically minimalist expressions of study assessment concepts. In the present
564 study, “items” are derived by a normalisation process from study assessment criteria
565 presented in study appraisal tools and described in focus group discussions, that potentially
566 relate to the internal validity of an *in vitro* study.

567 **Item bank** is a database of items.

568 **Normalisation** is the process of organizing data in a database. In the present example, this
569 involves identifying and consistently expressing the core bias concepts underlying the
570 assessment criteria applied by study appraisal tools.

571 **Risk of bias** is the potential for systematic error in the results or findings of a study or across
572 studies. Tools for assessing the internal validity of studies tend to focus on risk of bias, as
573 bias itself cannot usually be directly measured.

574 **Signalling questions** are the questions that the users of a validity assessment tool answer
575 in order to determine whether a given set of assessment criteria have been fulfilled.

576 Funding

577 Gro H. Mathisen, Gunn E. Vist, Paul Whaley, Richard A. White, Trine Husøy, Heather M.R.
578 Ames, Emma Di Consiglio, Kyriaki Machera, Eliana Spilioti, Anastasia Spyropoulou, Olga
579 Tcheremenskaia, Emanuela Testai, and Camilla Svendsen were supported by HORIZON-
580 HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-03, Grant [101057014]; Nicolas Roth was supported by The Swiss
581 State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract no.
582 22.00230.

583 The funding sources had no role in study design; in the collection, analysis and interpretation
584 of data; in the writing of the report; or in the decision to submit the article for publication.

585 Ethical considerations

586 Data Protection Impact Assessment has been performed and was approved by Norwegian
587 Institute of Public Health on February 7th, 2022, (Archive No 22/04212). Ethical approval is
588 not relevant since no biological materials or information on health will be collected.

589 Declaration of interests

590 The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship,
591 and/or publication of this manuscript.

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597 Paul Whaley.

598 **Funding acquisition:** Gro H. Mathisen and Camilla Svendsen.

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609 Husøy, Camilla Svendsen, Anna Beronius, Emma Di Consiglio, Ingrid L. Druwe, Thomas
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611 Robinson, Erwin Roggen, Andrew A. Rooney, Nicolas Roth, Eliana Spilioti, Anastasia
612 Spyropoulou, Olga Tcheremenskaia, Emanuela Testai, Mathieu Vinken, and Paul Whaley.

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